

Decision-making in complex sustainability: Using OPTamos in a multi-criteria process for residential area sustainability in suburban metropolitan Jakarta, Indonesia

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Abstract

Numerous studies have shown that the suburban region of Jakarta, commonly known as the Metropolitan suburb, is facing spill-over effects such as a surge in population growth and rapid development of residential areas by private developers. Although these residential areas have a positive impact on the regional economy, they also have adverse effects on the social and environmental aspects of the region, highlighting the need for a policy framework that ensures sustainability and addresses these impacts. To this end, this study proposes an innovative approach that utilizes an iterative transdisciplinary framework for Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) process, which engages key stakeholders in the decision-making process. This approach involves a comprehensive review of existing options and the development of new software called OPTamos to manage and process options provided by stakeholders effectively. The approach was applied to the sustainable residential areas decision-making process in South Tangerang and Depok City, which form the hinterland of Metropolitan Jakarta. The results produced acceptable options for sustainable residential areas in the suburban region of Metropolitan Jakarta, which satisfied key stakeholder criteria, and an action plan was formulated accordingly.

Keywords: residential area, policy, decision support, stakeholder participation

Introduction

The metropolitan suburbs of Jakarta are currently facing challenges in upholding their efficiency as a region, attributed to diverse economic, social, and environmental impacts. These impacts have led to various spill-over effects, manifested through a rise in population. This trend is widespread in many developing countries, and suburbs located in proximity to major cities such as DKI Jakarta, specifically Tangerang, South Tangerang, Depok, and Bekasi City, are not exempt from this phenomenon (refer to Fig. 1).

This phenomenon has resulted in several consequences, including the rise of urban sprawl, alterations in water usage, heightened demand for transportation that links individuals to the central urban area, and increased pressure on land. BPS statistics from the four regions demonstrate consistent growth in population over time. Specifically, between 2010 and 2019, Tangerang City saw an average population growth rate of 2.16 percent, South Tangerang City

experienced a rate of 3.56 percent, Depok City saw a rate of 3.53 percent, and Bekasi Municipality had a rate of 2.50 percent.

Fig 1. Location of South Tangerang, Tangerang, Bekasi, and Depok City as The Metropolitan Suburb of Jakarta

Increasing population growth will lead to a decrease in demand for land, particularly for housing. The Residential Area Corporation responded by constructing housing units in residential areas, which is supported by empirical evidence. The data shows that in South Tangerang City, the area of residential land increased from 60.07 percent in 2011 to 61.79 percent in 2016, equivalent to a conversion of 1.72 percent or 2.53 km² out of the total area of 147.19 km². In Depok City, the percentage of settlements in the total land area rose from 44.31 percent in 2005 to 53.24 percent in 2012. Similarly, in Bekasi City, the land used for settlements increased by 250.32 hectares or 58.48 percent from 2005 to 2014 (Cahyaningtyas & Rahayu 2015). In Tangerang City, the settlement area was only 22.13 percent of the total area in 2010, but it rose to 26.54 percent in 2013. On average, the residential land area in Tangerang City grew at a rate of 6 percent per year.

The increase in Land and Building Rights Acquisition Duty (BPHTB) from 2011 to 2016 confirmed additional data, indicating growth of 38.7 percent annually in South Tangerang City, 28.7 percent in Depok City, 22.56 percent in Bekasi City, and 33.11 percent in Tangerang City. Moreover, the available information demonstrated a positive increase in the contribution of the real estate sector to GDP (constant prices) between 2013-2017, with an average of 9.2 percent in South Tangerang City, 6.61 percent in Bekasi City, 1.57 percent in Depok City, and 7.5 percent in Tangerang City.

Numerous research studies have been dedicated to examining residential areas and their impact on people's agricultural livelihood strategies. These studies have found that the presence of residential areas has caused a shift in such strategies due to the transformation of agricultural land resulting from construction activities (Eltayeb *et al.*, 2013; Liu & Liu, 2016).

In addition, Clark (2001) asserts that residential areas have a detrimental effect on the development of social capital, place an undue burden on minority communities (Raguset, 2014), and contribute to economic inequality (Huang & Jiang, 2009; Yandri, 2014; Zhao, 2016; Roitman & Recio, 2019), as well as social and settlement segregation (Yandri 2015, Hwang, 2015).

According to Schram (1991), the establishment of residential areas is directly linked to a decreased level of political engagement among their inhabitants. This phenomenon has been corroborated through investigations conducted by Newman *et al.* (2013) in the United States and Yandri (2017) in South Tangerang Municipality, Indonesia.

Inquiring about methods for reconciling positive and negative impacts, the World Bank (2009) advocates for policy interventions at the national and regional levels, including district or city levels. Subsequently, the United Nations has incorporated housing concerns into their agenda, known as the New Urban Agenda. This agenda has been adopted by the Ministry of National Development Planning as a central planning theme, titled "Smart City Development," in 2015. Additionally, in 2014, the Ministry of PUPR of the Republic of Indonesia endeavored to devise a concept for the Sustainable Settlement Index, encompassing three dimensions that address social, economic, and environmental issues. The institutional aspects support the foundation of these three aspects.

A review of literature pertaining to the governance of residential areas indicates a wide-ranging set of issues. For instance, Ha (2008) identifies democratization, decentralization, and the role of non-governmental organizations as crucial concerns. Pendall (2008), on the other hand, delves into land-use regulations as a means of curbing urban sprawl, lowering regulatory barriers, devising incentive schemes, and extending subsidies. Furthermore, Tsenkova (2016), as outlined in the New Urban Agenda 2015, contends that effective governance of residential areas necessitates the involvement of policy-making actors, politicians, government officials, academics, and community leaders.

Despite ongoing academic debates, residential areas remain crucial in the implementation of sustainable principles. This is because housing represents a key public policy capable of influencing urban development and facilitating sustainable growth (Winston & Pareja 2008). However, the challenge lies in developing specific indicators for sustainability parameters, as this is no easy feat. One viable approach that is both academically rigorous and evidence-based involves crafting a policy framework with a set of strategies and policies aimed at promoting sustainability. Therefore, the preparation of policy strategies is a critical agenda in efforts to achieve sustainability. Accordingly, this paper presents a research report outlining strategies for promoting sustainability in residential areas within the suburban metropolitan area of Jakarta.

Theoretical Review

Academic usage of terms related to suburban areas differs considerably from their colloquial meaning. Terrence Mcgee (1991), as cited in Ortega (2012), introduced the concept of "desakota," which refers to a blend of intensive agricultural and non-agricultural activities situated along the corridors of major cities where residents engage in agricultural practices. This notion was subsequently adopted by Hudalah & Firman (2012) in their research on the

Jakarta Metropolitan City. Other terms used to describe suburban areas include “urban fringe” and “peri-urban,” which are employed in various contexts across several articles. The term “suburb” is also employed by Sonmez (2009) to study a suburban locality in the city of Izmir, Turkey.

Achieving a clear understanding of the concept of suburbs is essential, given the various terms used to describe it. According to Ann (2013), a clear definition is beneficial in multiple ways, such as guiding policy-making, formulating research problems and theories, and conducting field studies. While some may argue that precise definitions are only crucial for theoretical purposes, Ann (2013) argues that a clear definition is crucial for all three aspects mentioned above. Nonetheless, defining suburban areas remains a challenging task, as revealed by the analysis results. However, Ann (2013), citing Harris (2010), suggests that approaches based on location, density, and novelty could aid in defining suburbs.

In Indonesia, as in many developing countries, the suburban areas have experienced significant growth in both size and quantity. This expansion has had far-reaching effects on the surrounding areas, altering the economic, socio-cultural, ecological, and spatial structures of the suburbs. The resulting impacts include increased poverty (Curley, 2005), changes in the livelihood strategies of communities working in agriculture (Eltayeb et al., 2013; Liu & Liu, 2016), a decline in social capital (Clark, 2007), pressure on minority groups (Ragusett, 2014), and the proliferation of real estate and housing clusters (Leisch, 2002; Goix, 2005; Huang & Jiang, 2009; Serlin & Umilia, 2013; Güzey, 2014), leading to economic and income inequalities (Huang & Jiang, 2009; Yandri, 2014; Zhao, 2016), as well as social and housing segregation (Yandri, 2015; Hwang, 2015).

Fig 2. Distinguishing between residential areas and settlements in the suburban metropolitan region of Jakarta, Indonesia

The scientific literature employs diverse terms to denote human settlements and housing, including “housing,” “settlements,” “residential area,” and “neighborhood”. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, the term “housing” refers to the construction and designated use of houses or buildings intended to provide living spaces, often planned or provided by an

authority, with associated meanings. In contrast, “settlement” is defined as a place where people live together.

Moreover, the term “residential area” generally refers to an area with a higher proportion of housing compared to industrial or commercial structures, encompassing various types of dwellings such as single-family homes, multi-family apartments, or mobile homes. Some literature also uses the terms “housing cluster” (Hapsariniaty et al. 2013) or “housing complex” (Kerr 2008) interchangeably with residential areas. Additionally, in 2002, Leisch referred to residential areas as gated communities.

In Indonesia, legally and formally, housing is considered a subset of settlements. The defining characteristic that distinguishes settlements from housing is that settlements are typically constructed by individual communities, while housing is built by either private or government entities. As a result, it is relatively easy to distinguish a residential area as being housing. In Indonesia, privately built residential areas are sold back to the community, while government-built housing, such as police or university housing, serves as additional examples. From a spatial perspective, housing is generally more organized than settlements. This can be observed in Fig 2, which provides visual representations of the distribution patterns of housing and settlements.

Winston & Eastaway (2008) stressed the importance of sustainability in the realm of housing as it can significantly influence urban development and contribute to sustainable development. Sustainable development is still defined in economic development textbooks according to the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) as "patterns of development that meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (WCED 1987). Elkington (1997) subsequently introduced the concept of the "triple bottom line" (social, economic, and environmental) as fundamental in understanding sustainability and their interconnectedness.

Each sustainability element involves distinct objectives that humans aim to attain, and their attainment is crucial for sustainability. While it is challenging to achieve these elements, the absence of any one of them can render sustainability unclear. The three elements underscore the need for a cross-sectoral approach that integrates all aspects of all development processes. Consequently, Clark (2007) highlights the significance of a systemic approach and the promotion of feasible interactions among all elements. We refer to the interplay and interdependence of these elements as "complex sustainability".

On September 25, 2015, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) held a meeting at the United Nations Office in New York where the world-agreed policy framework was adopted, comprising seventeen objectives grouped into four categories: (1) Pillars of Social Development; (2) Pillars of Economic Development; (3) Pillars of Environmental Development; and (4) Pillars of Legal Development and Governance. The 11th objective, which falls under the Pillars of Social Development, is to ensure that cities and settlements are inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable.

Method

The present study focused on analyzing two suburbs, which were chosen as representatives of four suburbs in Metropolitan Jakarta. The selected suburbs were South Tangerang in Banten Province and Depok in West Java Province, and the aim was to assess whether there were any differences in policy perception between these two regions. Drawing on previous literature, we posited that the formulated options and criteria could serve as an

appropriate SRA (Sustainable Residential Area) strategy for the suburbs in Jakarta Metropolitan.

For this analysis, primary data was utilized which was collected through a survey questionnaire instrument. The sample selection process was purposive and involved stakeholders with knowledge of social issues related to residential areas in South Tangerang and Depok. Nine respondents were selected to address the research problem. Table 1 presents the distribution of stakeholder respondents associated with residential areas.

Table 1. Distribution of stakeholders in each region observed in OPTamos analysis

Stakeholders & numbers of respondent	Justification
The member of the legislative body (1)	Institutionally, the legislative body functions as a supervisory agency for the performance of municipal government. The legislative body comprises of various commissions responsible for managing economic, social, and local fiscal policies.
The local authority of the residential area, settlement, and land (1)	The said agency plays a crucial role in formulating policies related to residential areas and is highly significant to be considered as a sample.
The regional development planning agency (1)	The development planning agency in the region holds the responsibility of conducting development planning in both social and economic domains. It acts as an authorized body for the same.
The local authority of investment, and one-stop integrated services (1)	The agency is responsible for granting investment permits for the development of residential areas.
The local authority on the environment (1)	The agency is responsible for managing the environment within its jurisdiction and developing local policies related to environmental concerns.
The community representatives (1)	The input of communities, both within and outside the region, is considered essential as stakeholders to provide their feedback.
The residential area corporation (1)	This actor is the main actor of residential development.
Academic (1)	This actor's responsibility is to conduct an impartial evaluation of residential areas. Their expertise is associated with the field of development studies.

The study employed an analytical method called Options for Participatory Transformation and Sustainability Management (OPTamos), which is based on Hierarchical Process Analysis (AHP) and involves the participation of key stakeholders. AHP falls under the multicriteria analysis category, which has been used in previous studies to evaluate the sustainability of residential areas in Vilnius City, Lithuania, and the availability of housing in Liverpool, England. OPTamos is categorized under Multiple Criteria Decision Making

(MCDM) and has also been used in a study on land management in the Cuitzmala watershed in Mexico by Grima et al. (2017). The analytical procedures for OPTamos are presented in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Circular Processes in OPTamos Analysis

MCDM is a technique for making multi-variable decisions that do not rely on specific parameters. The technique places significant emphasis on weighting because it considers various criteria or variables and involves alternatives or policy options that can be taken. MCDM can be applied in decision-making processes because it ensures that each criterion and alternative is carefully considered before selecting the best policy option/alternative. According to Triantaphyllou et al. (2014) as cited in Mulliner et al. (2014), MCDM analysis generally comprises three stages: (1) identifying relevant criteria and alternatives; (2) determining numerical measures for the relative importance of the criteria and their impact on the alternatives; and (3) analyzing these numerical values to rank each alternative.

OPTamos is founded on the principle of pairwise comparison, and the mathematical process is executed through the AOX-dw software utilizing the Hierarchy Process Analysis (AHP) approach. The software allows direct pairing comparisons, and interest level measurement is conducted using an ordinal scale of 1-9, which includes options such as strongly agree, agree, somewhat agree, neutral, somewhat disagree, disagree, strongly disagree, and totally disagree. The overall mathematical process is performed using AOX-dw programming.

OPTamos, like other multicriteria analysis models, necessitates four principal input components. These include (1) objectives or goals that specify the primary aims of the analysis; (2) options or alternatives, derived from literature reviews, expert opinions, and policy analysis, which are elaborated upon through focused group discussions; (3) criteria that serve as the decision-making guide; and (4) weighting, which is executed through questionnaires distributed to respondents. The OPTamos analysis is conducted online via the internet portal <http://robin-decisionssupport.aau.at/> after registering and logging in (Fig 4).

Source: <http://robin-decisionssupport.aau.at/>, 2022

Fig 4. Login process to OPTamos software

The available policy options for spatial planning, from a technical standpoint, comprise homogeneous/concentrated and multi-functional (land use mixture) approaches (Rustiadi et al. 2011; Wunas 2011). In this study, three sustainable housing policy options were developed, and their descriptions are presented in Table 2. The aspects and criteria for each policy option were established based on a review of validated literature from Yandri et al. (2019), which is justified in accordance with the guide's instructions (Alpen-Adira Universitat n.d.). This study identified six aspects of sustainable housing areas that are characterized by (1) economy, (2) social, (3) environment, (4) infrastructure, (5) and technology, and their corresponding criteria are presented in detail in Table 3.

Table 2. SRA policy options in suburban metropolitan Jakarta

Policy option		Description
<i>Status Quo</i>	:	This policy is considered an “as is” and “as usual” policy, and it can also be classified as an existing policy that is currently in effect.
Homogeneous	:	The policy in question aims to concentrate residential spaces within residential areas, with the land being exclusively designated for residential purposes without providing any social, environmental, or economic space.

Multi-function/land use mixture	:	The integration of residential, social, environmental, and economic spaces is a defining characteristic of multifunctional residential areas.
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Table 3. Aspects and criteria of SRA in suburban metropolitan Jakarta

Aspect	Criteria	Justification
Economic	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Price 2. Micro, small, and medium economic activities (SMEs) within the region 	It is important that residential house prices are accessible to the community. SME activity can impact and interact with variations in economic activity. The fundamental concept is that activities are interdependent and cannot be separated from one another.
Social	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmental health 2. Community participation 3. Social activities 	Health is intertwined with environmental health, encompassing both physical and mental health as well as the facilities and infrastructure supporting them. Furthermore, community engagement is integral to promoting citizens' well-being.
Environment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Green open space 2. Clean water 3. Waste 4. Area view 	Green open space is significant for residents because it relates to the availability of play areas for children, directly related to sustainability. Clean water, waste, and regional scenery are influential agendas for sustainability.
Infrastructure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Social facilities (public health center, health clinic, places of worship, small market, playground, etc.) 2. Public facilities (streets, aqueduct, public lighting equipment, landfill, etc.) 3. Adaptation of residential areas to natural disasters and anthropogenic disasters 	It is crucial to establish this criterion as it pertains to the provision of infrastructure to support the well-being of the public residing in the residential area.
Technology	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of internet network and connection speed 2. CCTV cameras 	The internet has greatly increased the demand for suburban communities. Therefore, it is essential to include this indicator as a measure of SRA for testing purposes. One reason urban

		communities prefer to reside in residential areas is the desire for a sense of security (Leisch 2002). The availability of CCTV cameras is one measure that can be implemented to enhance this sense of security.
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Results and Discussion

The initial step of OPTamos involves assigning weights to policy options through stakeholder interviews. In the status quo option, the average stakeholder weighting for both suburban areas (South Tangerang City and Depok City) is 15 percent. The average weight for the homogeneous option is 27 percent, while that of the multifunctional land option is 58 percent. Based on this weighting, it appears that the multifunctional land option is favored by stakeholders as the optimal choice.

In the following stage, the selection of the optimal criteria is conducted based on the ones developed in Table 3, and the findings are presented in Fig 5 and Table 4. The results of the OPTamos algorithm test indicate that stakeholders in the residential area prefer clean water and waste management as the best criteria. Consequently, the environmental aspects are favored as the most suitable policy option for sustainable housing areas. This finding is reasonable as clean water is a basic need that should be provided to the households in the area, and it is also directly related to achieving the sixth goal in the environmental pillar of the SDGs indicator, which focuses on ensuring sustainable sanitation and clean water management.

Access to clean water is an essential requirement for sustaining life; however, limited availability or inadequate management of clean water has become a concern. It is worth noting that clean water is necessary in all areas as it supports various activities such as household, economic, and other daily activities. The Ministry of Public Works and the Settlement Republic of Indonesia has established standards for drinking water needs in rural and urban areas, which can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Standard drinking water needs in Indonesia

Region	Needs/capita/day (liter)
Rural	60
Small town	90
Medium city	110
Major cities	130
Metropolitan city	150

Source: The Ministry of Public Works and Settlements, Republic of Indonesia

According to the provided data, metropolitan suburbs such as DKI Jakarta are required to provide a minimum of 150 liters of clean water per capita per day. Therefore, policies that prioritize clean water are essential in achieving sustainable housing areas. This aligns with Regulatory of Government No. 16/2005, which requires local governments to ensure that everyone has access to clean drinking water for their basic needs on a daily basis to maintain a healthy, clean, and productive lifestyle.

Source: screenshot provided by OPTamos, 2022

Fig 5. The criterion for determining the level of interest in SRA

The government and large private developers involved in the development of South Tangerang must prioritize addressing the issue of limited availability of clean water in the area. The municipality of South Tangerang should initiate plans for managing clean water resources. Currently, drinking water for households, industries, and other economic activities is obtained from two main sources: PDAM Tangerang Regency and clean water installations managed by developers, as well as underground water. However, it is crucial for the South Tangerang City Government to establish an independent clean water treatment plant that is under direct supervision and management of the local government.

According to BPS data, in all four suburbs, twenty percent of the top-income communities still rely on drill wells or pumps to fulfill their clean water needs, with the proportion increasing to 29.19 percent among the spending group. Additionally, 60.07 percent of the total population in these areas still uses drill/pump wells to meet their water needs (Table 6). South Tangerang, with its rapid growth and infrastructure development, has a predominantly residential and settlement land use, covering 9,941.41 hectares or 67.54% of the

total area of 14,719 hectares. This highlights the increasing need for clean water to meet household activities in the area.

In the city of Depok, the usage of plumbing nests to fulfill clean water needs is still prevalent among the top-income communities with a proportion of 7.77 percent. Moreover, 81.62 percent of the total population still relies on pump wells for clean water (Table 6). Given that the land in Depok is mainly used for housing and settlements, the availability of clean water is crucial for the city's development.

Criteria	Status Quo	Homogen	Multifunction Area	Inconsistency ratio	% of importance
Price	15,07	27,40	57,53	0,05	7,16
SME's Activities	10,69	20,13	69,18	0,05	2,50
Environmental Health	12,50	23,21	64,29	0,05	7,75
Community Participation	8,47	23,73	67,80	0,08	1,59
Social Activities	9,35	17,76	72,90	0,05	2,00
Preservation Area	17,76	9,35	72,90	0,05	4,54
Clean Water	13,70	36,99	49,32	0,05	14,25
Waste Management	13,70	36,99	49,32	0,05	13,35
Social Facilities	9,88	18,97	71,15	0,03	5,29
Public Facilities	8,30	15,88	75,81	0,05	6,94
Disaster Adaptation	10,47	20,42	69,11	0,01	4,03
Internet Network	9,35	17,76	72,90	0,05	12,58
CCTV Cameras	9,35	17,76	72,90	0,05	11,45
Area Views	60,76	8,86	30,38	0,09	6,58
	14,99	23,41	61,61		

Source: screenshot provided by OPTamos, 2022

Fig. 6. The best criteria for SRA

Source: screenshot provided by OPTamos, 2020

Fig 7. The best policy options for SRA

Table 6. Percentage of households by primary water characteristics used for cooking/bathing/washing/and others in suburban metropolitan Jakarta

Suburban region	Characteristics	Primary Water Source Used by Households for Cooking/Washing/and -others					
		Refillable Bottled Water	Pipe water	Well Drill/Pump	Protected Well/Spring	Unprotected Wells/Springs	Other
South Tangerang	Gender						
	Male	2.97	8.11	84.09	4.64	0.15	0.03
	Female	0.82	14.58	73.83	9.50	0.46	0.80
	Production quartile						
	Bottom 40 percent	2.21	1.33	92.03	4.05	0.38	0.00
	40 percent center	2.92	4.52	87.25	5.13	0.12	0.07
	Top 20 percent	3.22	29.19	60.07	7.12	0.00	0.41
Depok	Gender						
	Male	6.75	5.78	79.79	7.32	0.18	0.17
	Female	4.08	7.27	80.73	7.92	0.00	0.00
	Production quartile						
	Bottom 40 percent	5.09	3.49	77.65	12.92	0.44	0.41
	40 percent center	5.69	7.14	80.92	6.25	0.00	0.00
	Top 20 percent	9.66	7.77	81.62	0.95	0.00	0.00

Source: Local Statistical Bureau of South Tangerang and Depok City, 2018

According to various research reports, the rapid development of land use for settlements and offices is cited as one of the reasons for the reduction in water absorption areas. As a result, some areas in South Tangerang, such as North Serpong and Serpong District, are experiencing a clean water crisis. The availability and proper management of clean water are crucial for supporting development in any area. Hence, any development should prioritize environmental aspects and promote sustainable development. Despite this, many urban and rural communities are still unserved by drinking water networks, and not all urban areas have access to piping networks.

Source: screenshot provided by OPTamos, 2020

Fig 8. Sensitivity analysis in each criterion on paired comparisons

Furthermore, waste management is a crucial policy option that must be considered to achieve sustainable housing in suburban residential areas with limited land. According to data from the local Environment Agency, the average daily household waste production in all four suburbs is alarmingly high. For instance, in South Tangerang City, the average household waste produced per day reaches 1000 tons, 1400 tons per day in Tangerang City, 1286 tons per day in Depok City, and 1800 tons per day in Bekasi Municipality.

Upon analyzing the data, it becomes evident that waste management is crucial in achieving sustainable housing areas. In line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), waste management is a key priority in achieving SDG 11, which aims to create inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and settlements. One of the indicators in this goal is the percentage of urban waste that is managed appropriately.

In terms of priority, both clean water and waste management have the highest value among all options presented, including the status quo, homogeneous, and multifunctional options (see Table 2). This suggests that regardless of the policy options chosen, clean water and waste management should be prioritized in order to achieve sustainable housing. Moreover, technology is also considered a high-priority aspect. Two criteria related to technology, namely internet networks and CCTV cameras, are deemed essential by stakeholders for a residential area. According to the OPTamos algorithm calculation, the importance values for these criteria are 12.64 and 11.50, respectively. If these criteria are met, they can contribute to achieving a SRA.

Table 7. Youth composition in suburban metropolitan Jakarta

Age Group	Suburban region			
	South Tangerang	Tangerang	Depok	Bekasi
15 – 19	127.892	163.726	121,180	242.879
20 – 24	140.117	201.482	136,140	266.528
25 – 29	154.212	226.498	133,636	295.052
30 – 34	159.648	221.788	113,630	269.446
35 – 39	156.648	196.986	91,459	237.452
40 – 44	144.909	173.269	71,502	205.672
Amount	883.426	1.183.749	667.547	1.517.029
Proportion to total population	52,07	54,16	58,38	55,50

Sumber: Local Statistical Bureau

This criterion is closely linked to the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically the ninth objective which focuses on developing resilient infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and fostering innovation. Three indicators are associated with this criterion, including the percentage of the population with access to mobile broadband, the percentage of individuals who own a mobile phone, and the percentage of individuals who use the internet.

In terms of characteristics of suburban areas occupied by the urban middle class, the internet network and the quality of its connections are the most suitable options, considering the nature of their work, income, and age (Table 7). These characteristics are associated with a high level of information consumption. According to the National Statistical Bureau's data in 2018, internet users are mainly between the ages of 15 to 34 years old, with the highest usage rate among those between 15 to 19 years old, followed by those between 20 to 24 years old, 25 to 29 years old, and 30 to 34 years old. BPS also reported that most internet users work in various fields such as entrepreneurship, teaching, online trading, consulting, civil servants, and employees.

The CCTV camera criteria has been identified by stakeholders as the most important criterion for achieving sustainable housing areas. CCTV cameras are considered an essential infrastructure in residential areas and are important in reducing criminal activity. This is consistent with previous studies that have shown that people prioritize security when choosing a place to live, and that CCTV cameras are an important supporting facility (Leisch, 2002). The inclusion of CCTV cameras in residential areas aligns with the 16th SDG goal of promoting peace, justice, and resilient institutions, which is measured by three indicators: (1) the decrease in the number of murders in the past year, (2) the decrease in the proportion of the population who are victims of violent crimes, and (3) the increase in the proportion of people who feel safe walking alone in their area of residence.

In addition, the identified criteria exhibit varying levels of importance across different aspects, namely economic, social, environmental, infrastructure, and technology, each of which has its own set of priorities. As shown in Table 8, the top criterion for each aspect is highlighted. In the economic aspect, affordable housing prices are the most crucial criterion. Policymakers should prioritize environmental health in the social aspect, as this criterion is deemed most important by stakeholders. For the environmental aspect, the availability of clean water should be given priority by policymakers, as it has the highest degree of interest compared to other criteria.

Table 8. The best SRA policy options

Aspects	Best criteria options	The best policy options in SRA
Economic	Affordable price	Multifunctional land
Social	Environmental health	
Environment	Availability of clean water	
Infrastructure	Availability of public facilities (streets, waterways, public lighting equipment, landfills, etc.)	
Technology	Internet network availability	

In terms of infrastructure, it is recommended that policymakers prioritize the availability of public facilities, including roads, waterways, public lighting tools, and landfills, when developing sustainable housing areas. Additionally, policymakers should pay attention to the availability of internet networks in the technology aspect, as it received the highest degree of interest among other criteria. To achieve sustainable housing areas, it is important to include all of these criteria in multifunctional land policy options (Fig. 5). Sensitivity analysis can be used to evaluate the model by changing the weight of criteria in paired comparison, as shown in Fig. 8.

The OPTamos algorithm calculation reveals that altering the weight of criteria in paired comparison does not alter the policy scenario. The optimal multifunctional land policy option still remains with a percentage value of 59.8%. Sensitivity analysis indicates a slight decrease in the percentage of the multifunctional land scenario from 61.3% to 59.8% (as presented in Fig. 9).

The sensitivity analysis indicates that the environmental criterion, in conjunction with multifunctional land policy options, holds greater significance compared to other dimensions (economic, social, infrastructure, and technology) in establishing sustainable housing areas. These findings align with earlier research (Amado et al. 2017) conducted to develop an all-inclusive residential area in East Timor. Such inclusive residential areas necessitate the utilization of multifunctional land, which is viewed as a crucial element in promoting sustainable housing areas.

The multifunctional land policy option is highly favored by most stakeholder respondents, and it has a crucial role in realizing sustainable housing areas in the metropolitan suburbs of Jakarta. According to Suryani & Tarigan (2009), land use is a vital factor in successful sustainable urban planning, which aims to achieve efficient energy and natural resource use, reduce costs, and promote economic and social diversity. Some land-use planning strategies for sustainable urban planning include multifunctional land, more compact or dense land use, integration between land use and infrastructure, land use for small-scale activities, and the provision of more open space.

Our empirical study provides complementary insights into the concept of multifunctional land in suburban areas, which has been discussed in previous studies such as McGee (1991) and is commonly applied in Southeast Asian countries. The concept of multifunctional land development aims to reduce energy consumption, achieve economic and social diversity, and manage metropolitan growth. In multifunctional areas, diverse urban activities are concentrated

in a well-designed physical configuration, with internal circulation and external accessibility. These activities can include residential areas, shopping areas, markets, offices, hotels, recreation areas, sports facilities, and parking. The areas are physically and functionally integrated, with close proximity to one another and easy accessibility by foot or public transportation.

The development of multifunctional areas can be approached through three methods: (1) increasing land use intensity, (2) increasing the variety of land functions, and (3) integrating various activity functions. These concepts can be applied at different scales, including multifunctional buildings, areas, and transit zones, as suggested by Waddel (2010).

Amado et al. (2017) argue that homes play a more significant role in developing countries compared to developed countries since they are not only used for earning a livelihood, working, and socializing, but also as a site for preserving cultural heritage. Consequently, homes have the potential to serve as a key strategy for development. In the context of residential areas, the study by Amado et al. (2017) provides robust support for the notion that residential areas can serve as multi-functional land.

In this context, it is evident that designing residential areas with multifunctional land is the most suitable policy implication. It means that residential areas should not be limited to just housing units, as such an approach cannot support sustainable housing areas. Therefore, the realization of sustainable suburbs would be challenging. The promotion of such an approach can be achieved through public policies in the form of regulations and technical guidelines. The drafting of such regulations can be done by the suburbs while considering the authority distribution between the local and central governments in line with regional autonomy. The spirit of this approach is also supported by the Law No. 1/2011 on Housing and Residential Areas in Indonesia.

Furthermore, a set of technical regulations has been developed to support the draft policy at the regional level for the guidelines on residential area development. These regulations, along with the draft policy, can serve as a reference for government officials in suburban cities who are tasked with designing regulations for the planning of multifunctional residential areas. Some of the technical regulations include: (1) regulation of the Minister of Public Housing No. 34/2006 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Integrated Infrastructure, Facilities, and Public Utilities (PSU) of Residential Areas; (2) regulation of the Minister of State of Public Housing of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2011 concerning Infrastructure, Facilities, and Public Utilities (PSU) of Housing and Residential Areas; and (3) regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 9 of 2009 concerning Guidelines for the Delivery of Infrastructure, Facilities, and Utilities for Housing and Settlements in the Region.

Conclusion

The study examined three scenarios as alternatives to the current SRA policies, namely the status quo, homogeneous land, and multifunctional land, by considering twelve criteria that cover economic, social, environmental, infrastructure, and technological parameters. The results of the analysis revealed that the implementation of a multifunctional land policy is the best option to achieve the SRA, with a focus on meeting criteria such as affordable house prices, environmental health, availability of clean water, availability of public facilities (e.g., roads, waterways, public lighting devices, landfills, etc.), and availability of internet networks. Thus, all of these criteria must be integrated into the multifunctional land policy.

The superiority of multifunctional land in achieving sustainable residential areas (SRA) is mainly attributed to the characteristics of suburban cities, which experience a rapid increase in population and consequently have a growing demand for public facilities such as clean water,

roads, waterways, public lighting devices, and landfills. The fulfillment of these facilities is crucial to ensure a healthy residential environment with satisfactory quality, and it directly contributes to achieving the sixth goal of the environmental pillar in the SDGs indicator, which aims to ensure the availability of clean water management and sustainable sanitation.

The policy implication of this study is that the city government in suburban Metropolitan Jakarta must enact regulations to ensure that residential areas have multifunctional land use. Such land should not be limited to housing units alone but should include a combination of various functions that support economic and social activities. The study's main contribution lies in using the OPTamos Model for assessing and determining the best strategy for SRA development. This model is a participatory-based sustainability analysis tool that involves the perception of key stakeholders. Additionally, the study introduced new parameters for SRA, namely infrastructure and technology, to accommodate suburban communities' preferences, which differ from those of rural communities. The use of the OPTamos Model helped refine previous findings and provided insights into the elements of sustainable development that are essential for suburban areas.

Notably, the OPTamos model has certain limitations, as the selection of the best alternatives is influenced by the subjective interests of stakeholders. To overcome this limitation, future studies may integrate stakeholder perception data, which are primary data, with objective and quantifiable evidence obtained through secondary sources. This approach is expected to enhance the credibility and reliability of the analysis results.

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